

The Teacher's Problem in Implementing Curriculum 2013 at State Senior High School 3 of West Halmahera

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Abstract

This research attempted to figure out the problems that teachers in senior high schools dealt with in implementing Curriculum 2013 and what efforts they had taken to overcome the problems. By employing descriptive qualitative method, the researcher took data by distributing questionnaire and by observing the classroom processes. Two senior high school teachers were involved as the participants. They were English teachers in the Senior High School 3 on West Halmahera. From the analysis of the data, it has been found that some problems regarding to the improvement of the students' academic improvement and some efforts to overcome the problems were discussed.

Keywords: *curriculum 2013, English teaching and learning, teaching problem.*

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1. Background

Curriculum has been generally described as a rule that government made for better education. This is the reason why curriculum is a dynamic document which is usually developed, revised, and/or replaced. The changes happened on the curriculum are mainly intended to match a number of variables in education field ranging from the students, social environment, to industrial demands. Curriculum 2013 is one of the curricula which comes to add or even to replace the previous curriculum, school-based curriculum or KTSP (in school) or competence-based curriculum or KBK (in higher education).

Basically, all curriculums focus on the students' competencies because at the heart of education is to produce competent graduates. However, different curriculum defines competency in different way. Curriculum 2013 defines competency based on the Indonesian Education System Policy. The policy integrates three dimensions: attitude, knowledge, and skill. However, it has been assumed that the implementation of this curriculum was being focused on the skill and knowledge dimension whereas the attitude dimension was not enough paid attention.

2. Theoretical Basis

2.1. Defining Curriculum

Etymologically, curriculum is derived from the Latin word “curriculae” which stands for “distance.” Historically, this word means the distance that a runner must reach. In education, this word has been interpreted as the outcome that the education must attain. In the past, curriculum is described as the period of education that must be taken by students to obtain degree. Here, curriculum has been seen as the finish line of a race.

Terminologically, different experts have different interpretation toward this word. Old fashioned interpretation says that curriculum is the subject that the students must attend to earn the degree or diploma. The modern or new view, as proposed by Romine (1854), sees curriculum as the organized courses, activities, and experiences which pupils have under direction of the school.

2.2. Curriculum 2013

As an instrument of education, curriculum is a dynamic education plan which is subject to changes. It is noted in the decree of Indonesian Education and Culture Ministry (number 59, 2014) that curriculum 2013 is a competency-based curriculum. This curriculum was considered as a response toward various criticisms addressed to the previous curriculum, school-based curriculum.

Curriculum 2013 was intended as one of the government’s efforts to resolve the various problems faced in the education field today. It is intended to generate productive, creative, innovative, and affective graduates through the strengthening of attitudes, skills, and knowledge.

Implementation of a curriculum means the process of applying ideas, concepts, policies, or innovations in the form of practical actions to give effect in the form of changes in knowledge, skill, and attitude. Oxford dictionary defines the word implementation as putting effect on something. Therefore, it can be simply said that curriculum implementation is the actualization of the curriculum in the form of learning. Miller and Sellar (1990) mention that curriculum implementation can be identified with the instruction. Curriculum implementation is, in short, defined as a planned activity carried out by reference to certain norms to achieve the objective of the activity.

3. Method

This research was conducted as a descriptive research. According to Nunan (1992), descriptive method is a method in examining the status of the group of people, an object, and a set of condition, a system of thought, or a class of events in the present. This definition matches the

purpose of this study where the curriculum and its implementation are the object and class of events. The purpose of this study is to build a description about the investigated objectives.

The data were collected through questionnaire and observation. The questionnaire consists of the statements ranging from the teacher’s understanding on the curriculum to the teacher’s preparation before implementing the curriculum. Meanwhile, the observation took place in the classroom where the researcher observed the process of the curriculum implementation.

4. Finding and Discussion

Observation conducted in the classroom has been termed into three items. The first item (coded as 0) represents the teacher’s activity in preparing the lesson. The second item (coded as 1) represents the teacher’s activity in conducting the classroom process. The third item (coded as 2) represents the teacher’s activity in evaluating the classroom. These three items were broken down further into 12 sub-items. Those items were scored during the observation process.

There are three scores used in this observation; 0 means that the activity was not conducted; 1 means that the activity was conducted but low in exposure; and 2 the activity was done in sufficient exposure. The following table shows the observation scores taken from the two teachers.

No	Items	Scores	
		T1	T2
1	Means of learning preparation	1	1
2	Communicating previous learning	1	1
3	Linking with past lesson	1	1
4	Linking material with everyday environment	0	0
5	Suitability of the material discussed with indicator	1	1
6	Giving waiting time to students to answer question	1	0
7	Giving students opportunity to ask question	0	0
8	Mastering teaching and learning media	1	1
9	Giving motivation and reinforcement	0	1
10	Guiding students to draw conclusion	0	1
11	Linking material with future lesson	1	1
12	Conduct evaluation	1	1

The frequency of 0 score in the table above indicates that the teachers deal with the following problems:

- It is hard for the teachers to link the material with the everyday life or everyday environment;
- It is hard for the teacher to manage time for students to answer the question;
- It is hard for the teachers to have the students asking questions;
- It is hard for the teacher to motivate and reinforce the students for further learning;

e. It is hard for the teacher to guide the students to draw conclusion.

The possible factors that emerge the problems vary from point to point. Point (a) can be caused by the teacher's dependency toward the textbooks or material they used in the classroom. This leads to the limitation of creativity in managing and exemplifying the material based on daily life experiences or environment (Olivia, 1982). Point (b) can be caused by the lack of time management. Sometimes the students need more time to think before answering the question given by the teacher because most of the students highly worry to give incorrect answer. Point (c) can be the subsequent problem generated from point (b) which is caused by the lack of time management. Point (d) can be caused by the teacher's perspective toward learning purpose. It is possible that the teacher assumed that his duty is to transfer the knowledge, not to transform the students. Point (e) is possibly based on the teacher's assumption that it is not the students' right to conclude the material delivered in the classroom.

Most of the pointed problems above are relevant to the assumption that the curriculum 2013 implementation today is lacking of attention toward the attitude dimension. It can be seen obviously that the points above are related to the generation of students' positive attitude toward learning.

Data from the questionnaire revealed the basic reasons of the problems noted above. It was found that the reasons are:

- a. The teachers' understanding on the curriculum 2013 was worthy to be developed;
- b. It was new for the teachers to implement curriculum 2013;
- c. The teachers were not given the written guide to implement the curriculum;
- d. The teachers were not trained to evaluate and to assess learning progress based on the curriculum 2013;
- e. The teachers did not have any reference (besides the written guidance) in implementing the curriculum.

It can be clearly seen that the teachers need to be trained and guided in implementing new curriculum. As a dynamic document, the new curriculum subjects to changes and addition of new items is common (Richards, 2002).

It is possible that the teachers were accustomed to use traditional teaching manner rather than what the curriculum points to do. The habit that the teachers hold can make the curriculum implementation meaningless. It can posit the curriculum as the document without realization.

It was noted that the school has arranged an evaluation on the curriculum 2013 implementation in that certain school. This evaluation is the effort that the school does as the effort to resolve the problem noted and discussed above. However, it does not change the fact that

the teachers need more than evaluation. The teachers need certain training and written guide on implementing the curriculum 2013 because it is new for them.

5. Conclusion

Based on the short discussion above, it can be concluded that the teachers' problems are related to the attitude dimension of the curriculum 2013 and this is directly related to the time management and old-fashioned perspective on the teaching process. The data revealed that the curriculum 2013 is new for the teachers and therefore they need certain training and written guidance in implementing the curriculum. The school has arranged an evaluation process regarding to the curriculum implementation but they absolutely need to arrange the training for the teachers.

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